

The Relationship between Religion and Adolescent Depression in Ekiti State of Nigeria

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Abstract

Religious practices, depressive symptoms, and bouts of major depression are widespread among adolescents in all countries of the world, but there has not been an agreement on their relationship. This paper attempts to find out a possible relationship between religion and depression among adolescents in Ekiti State Nigeria. The descriptive research of the survey type was adopted for the study. The sample consisted of 520 adolescents that were selected using a multistage sampling technique from the 16 local government areas of Ekiti State of Nigeria. A questionnaire on religious practices and depression designed by the researcher and based on the works of Flugum (1995) and Beck (1996) was used to collect data and the data collected were analysed using frequency counts, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and student t-test to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results show that the adolescents in Ekiti State are religious and there is no significant relationship between religion and depression. However, there is a significant difference in the incidence of depression among Christian and Muslim adolescents in the Ekiti State of Nigeria. It was recommended that school counsellors should employ the use of religious involvement in counselling through various religious practices, such as prayer or meditation, to reduce tension and anxiety among the adolescents.

Keywords: Religion, Religious Practices, Depressive Symptoms, and Depression

Introduction

Ekiti State is one of the states in Southwest Nigeria with its people practicing the three major religions recognized in Nigeria; Christianity, Islamic and Traditional religions. The term religion has been given various definitions depending on various interests. However, religion according to Koenig, King, and Carson (2012), is a multidimensional construct that includes beliefs, behaviors, rituals, and ceremonies that may be held or practiced in private or public settings but is in some way derived from established traditions that developed over time within a community. Religiosity is also seen as one's relationship with a particular faith, tradition or doctrine about a divine other or supernatural power (Reich, Oser, & Scarlett, 1999). Although religious practices differ by culture, political boundary, local community, and individual, some form of religion is influential, even central, in the lives of many people across the globe (Hood Jr., Spilka, Hunsberger & Gorsuch, 2003; Fisher, 2005). Religion seems to be significant in the lives of Ekiti people as most of them are adherents of one form of religion or the other and the adolescents seem to be divided into the three forms of religions identified above. Meanwhile, Bonelli, Dew, Koenig, Rosmarin and Vasegh (2012) observed that a significant proportion of the world's population has religious beliefs and practices that are important to daily life. This study is focused on the association between Christian and Muslim religions, and depression among adolescents.

Religion can be seen as an important context for human development (Pargament, 2007) because it provides a means of socialization in areas such as moral behavior and offers emotional support to individuals from the cradle to the grave (Roof, 1999). Given cognitive advances during adolescence including increased abilities to think abstractly and understand symbolism (Donelson, 1999), it is important to study the impact of religion during this stage. Meanwhile, observation shows that religious involvement is common among adolescents and can be seen as a very important component of their daily lives in Ekiti State.

Although there are many genetic, developmental, and environmental factors contributing to the onset and maintenance of depression, it has been found that failure to cope with life stress is often a major underlying factor (Auerbach, Abela, Zhu, & Yao, 2010). Also, a large and growing volume of research suggests that religious or spiritual beliefs and practices may be used to cope with or adapt to stressful life circumstances (Braam, Schrier, Tuinebreijer, Beekman, Dekker & de Wit, 2010; Carpenter, Laney & Mezulis, 2012; Behere, Das, Yadav & Behere, 2013; Radzi, Ramly, Ghazali, Sipon & Othman, 2014; Gardner, Krageloh & Henning, 2014 and Adam, Abela, Zhu, & Yao, 2016). Many religious houses in the State are mostly seen as havens of relaxation for the adolescents where problems could be addressed and solved. This might be due to the general view of religion as being concerned with

the comfort of man in this world and also in the life hereafter. Petts and Anne Jolliff (2008) argued that if religious involvement is capable of reducing life stress by helping people to cope better, then it may help to prevent the development of depression or speed the attenuation of a depressive episode and/or depressive symptoms. They further posit that religious beliefs may also create high standards that are difficult to live up to, resulting in the sense of failure and guilt. In other words, those unable to live according to these standards may face rejection from their faith community, resulting in social isolation. This may develop into major depression. Despite the fact that different religious traditions promote different specific beliefs, issues, and different behavioral expectations, those differences do not translate, in some cases, into varying levels of adolescent well-being (Stolz, Olsen, Henke, & Barber, 2013). However, some other studies posit that there is a positive association between religious coping, stress and depressive symptoms among adolescents (Carpenter, Laney & Mezulis, 2011). Amrai and Sharifian (2011) found a high negative correlation between religious orientation and depression. According to them, reinforcement and assimilation of religious values can enhance increased mental health.

Also, while working on depression and its relation to loneliness and religiosity in Indonesian Muslim adolescents, Purwono and French (2016) discovered that religiosity was negatively associated with depression despite controlling for loneliness, gender, and grade. Also, that religiosity was not associated with loneliness, suggesting that some religious practices might be related to depression (Purwono & French, 2016). Waite (2017) however, submits that there was no significant correlation between the self-reported level of religiosity and depression among sampled Kenyans.

Blazer (2011) also observed that depression which has been the most frequently studied of the psychiatric disorders in relation to religion or spirituality and suggested that guilt associated with depression is often connected with a religious belief system, and apparent depressive symptoms are associated with religious experiences. While presenting data from a longitudinal study of offspring from a sample of depressed and non-depressed subjects to determine if religion or spirituality influenced the onset and course of major depression over the 10 years of follow-up, Miller, Wickramaratne, Gameroff, Sage, Tenke and Weissman (2012) found, among individuals who are affiliated as either Protestant or Catholic, and have reported religion or spirituality as highly important, were 76% less likely to experience an episode of major depression during the follow-up. A study by Berry (2011) supported a direct and protective effect over time between religion and depression, but a buffering effect on the relationship between stress and depression was not found. Possibly because a stronger relationship with God will predict fewer depression and anxiety symptoms for some youths whose mothers, according to Goeke-Morey, Taylor, Merilees, Shirlow, and Cummings (2014) used more religious coping techniques, it submitted that through all aspects of religion may inhibit the development of depression, there seems not to be a relationship between religion and depression (Berry, 2011).

From the foregoing, religion appears to be related to depression in one way or another. Given the coping behavior and reported effectiveness of religion (for example, Berry, 2011), and the serious disability that depression causes, efforts can be made to understand better how religion might impact on the mental health of adolescents. To pilot this study, the following questions were raised:

1. Are the adolescents in Ekiti State religious?
2. Would adolescents in Ekiti State Nigeria manifest depressive symptoms?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between religion and depression among adolescents in Ekiti State.
2. There is no significant difference in the incidence of depression between Christian and Muslim adolescents in Ekiti State.

Research Method

Descriptive research of the survey type was used for this study. The population for this study consisted of all the adolescents, both male, and female, in secondary schools in the Ekiti State of Nigeria, comprising of sixteen local government areas. The State is majorly agrarian and populated by the Yoruba ethnic group with similar language and

dialect. Most of them are also adherents of the Christian and Muslim religions. All the government owned secondary schools including coeducational and non-coeducational schools in the State were used for the study. The age group of adolescents that participated in the study was between 12 – 18years.

The sample for this study consisted of 520 adolescents (male and female) selected through a multistage sampling technique. The first stage involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select three local government areas from each of the three senatorial districts of the state.

The second stage entailed the use of purposive selection to select five government owned secondary schools in each of the local government areas earlier selected. The third stage also involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select thirty-six students from each of the schools selected, but in all, a total of 520 adolescents participated in the study.

A questionnaire designed by the researcher and titled “Religion and Depression Questionnaire” (REDEQ) was used to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of three sections A, B, and C. Section A sought information on demographic characteristics of the respondents, such as sex, age, religion and location.

Section B contained 10 items adapted from Flugum (1995) in Waite (2011) on the religious practices of the adolescents. Respondents were required to rate themselves on 10 different religious practices based on a 4-point Likert Scale 1 – 4. Items 1 – 4 were rated 1 (Never); 2 (Once a month); 3 (A few times a month); and 4 (Several times a week). Respondents were expected to rate the extent by which they agree with the statements on items 5-10 ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree); 2 (Disagree); 3 (Agree); to 4 (Strongly Agree). The scores of each respondent on the items were summed up to give the respondent’s degree of religious practices. The maximum score obtainable on the scale of the religious practice is 40. Respondents that scored 20 and above were categorized as being religious while those that scored below 20 were regarded as not being religious.

Section C is a modified form of Beck’s Depression Inventory (1996) which has been found to have high validity rating of 0.77 and reliability of 0.93 (Farinde, 2013). It consisted of 21 groups of statements on different symptoms of depression such as sadness, pessimism, failure, loss of pleasure, guilty feeling, self-dislike, and so on. Each statement is rated on a modified 4-point Likert Scale 1 – 4, with the respondents picking which of the statements best describe the way he or she is feeling in recent time and at the moment. Respondents were expected to pick just one out of the options. The scores of each respondent on each of the items were summed to give the respondent’s level of depression. The total score of obtainable is 84. Respondents were categorized as ‘Low,’ ‘Moderate’ and ‘High’ levels of depression based on percentile formula, that is Low (21.00 – 27.97), Moderate (27.98 – 55.97) and High (55.98 – 84.00).

The REDEQ was subjected to Face, Content and Construct validity. The reliability coefficient was 0.75 and found significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The instrument was administered to 540 respondents by the researcher and two trained research assistants. However, a total of 520 copies of the questionnaire were collected and analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics of frequency counts, percentages, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and student’s t-test.

Results

In order to find an answer to the question of whether or not adolescents in Ekiti State are religious, scores on religious participation were computed, and the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Religious Status of Adolescents in Ekiti State

<i>Religious Status</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Not Religious (1 - 19)	181	34.8
Religious (20 - 40)	339	65.2
Total	520	100.0

Table 1 shows that 181 respondents representing 34.8% of the total sample expressed low participation in religious activities while 339(65.2%) expressed high participation in religious activities and were classified as being religious. This implies that a higher proportion of adolescents in Ekiti State were religious.

In answering the question of whether or not adolescents in Ekiti State Nigeria manifest depressive symptoms, scores on depressive symptoms among adolescents were computed, and the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Manifestation of Depressive Symptoms among Adolescents in Ekiti State

<i>Level of Depressive Symptoms</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Low (21.00-27.97)	214	41.2
Moderate (27.98-55.97)	298	57.3
High (55.98-84.00)	8	1.5
Total	520	100.0

Table 2 shows that 214 respondents representing 41.2% of the total sample manifested low level of depressive symptoms, 298 (57.3%) had moderate level while 8 (1.5%) had a high level of depressive symptoms. This implies that more adolescents in the Ekiti State of Nigeria manifested a moderate level of depressive symptoms than those who manifested low or high levels with only 1.5% of them exhibiting high depressive symptoms.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between religion and depression among adolescents.

In testing the hypothesis, scores relating to religious practices and depression among the adolescents were computed, and these scores were subsequently subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that religion does not significantly relate to depression among adolescent ($r=-0.036$, $p>0.05$). Though the relationship between religion and depression among adolescents is low, negative and statistically not significant at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that religion is not significantly related to depression among adolescent.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the incidence of depression between Christian and Muslim adolescents in Ekiti State.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to the incidence of depression among Christian and Muslim adolescents were computed and compared for statistical significance using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: t-test Comparison of Depression between Christian and Muslim Adolescents

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t_{cal}</i>	<i>t_{table}</i>
Christian	270	31.96	9.93	518	2.924*	1.960
Muslim	250	33.56	12.04			

* $p<0.05$

Table 3 shows that $t_{cal}(2.924)$ is greater than $t_{table}(1.960)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the incidence of depression among Christian and Muslim adolescents in Ekiti State. Muslim adolescents had a higher mean score of 33.56 than their Christian (mean=31.96) counterparts. This implies that the incidence of depression is higher among Muslim adolescents.

Discussion

The result of this study showed that adolescents in the Ekiti State of Nigeria are religious with many of them expressing high participation in religious activities. This agrees with the findings of Arora and Gupta (2014) which revealed that adolescents are highly religious, but the religiosity level is without regard to their age. This might be due to the adolescents' quest for identity especially religious identity, as they begin to experience strong emotions and rapid mood swings at this stage of their development. It might have also arisen from the buffering effects of religion which might have motivated them to be faithful to the supernatural powers of religion.

The study further revealed that depression is being manifested by a large number of adolescents in the Ekiti State of Nigeria. This should be a cause of concern to the guidance counsellor and even the few that manifested high level depression. This might not be unconnected with the varying daily and developmental challenges the adolescents face both at homes and in school. The finding is consistent with the findings of Adeniyi, Okafor, and Adeniyi (2012), Fatiregun and Kumapayi (2014) and Ibimiluyi (2017) which established the prevalence of depression among adolescents in southwest Nigeria.

The study further revealed that religion is not significantly related to the development of depression among adolescents in the Ekiti State of Nigeria. This supports the views of some researchers (for example, Berry, 2011; Purwono & French, (2016) and Waite (2017) that while religiosity was not associated with some symptoms of depression, there might be a relation between some religious practices and depression. However, given the buffering effects of religion, individuals who are religious might not likely experience bouts of major depression. In essence, some religious practices such as frequency of attendance and high level of commitment to religious activities might reduce the susceptibility of individuals to the development of depressive symptoms.

The results of this study also showed that there is a significant difference in the incidence of depression among Christian and Moslem adolescents in Ekiti State. Specifically, the incidence of depression is higher among Muslim adolescents. This runs contrary to the findings of Iqbal, Ahmad and Ayub (2012) which states that religious minority adolescents that are Christians and Hindus are inclined to have higher levels of depression than their dominant Muslim counterparts in Pakistan. There could be other factors other than religious practices that control the manifestation of depression. Plante and Sharma (2001) had suggested that different cultural contexts may contribute to the dissimilarity of the association between religiosity and depression.

Based on the finding of this study it is recommended that school counsellors should employ the use of religious involvement in counselling through various religious practices, such as prayer or meditation, to reduce tension and anxiety which might eventually develop into major depression.

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